

ARE THE “CIRCLES” OF MARATHON (TEXAS, USA) A TIMID NORTH AMERICAN VERSION OF THE NAZCA LINES?

¿SON LOS CÍRCULOS DE MARATHON (TEXAS, USA) UNA TÍMIDA VERSIÓN NORTEAMERICANA DE LAS LÍNEAS DE NAZCA?

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ABSTRACT

Marathon town in northern-west Texas, shows curious circles that can be seen from the space but difficultly from land. These “circles” have been found thanks to new satellite images, with quite non similar images positioned in other United State of America location.

KEY WORDS: Archaeology, Apache, geoglyphs.

RESUMEN

La ciudad de Marathon en el noroeste de Texas muestra curiosos círculos que se pueden ver desde el espacio, pero difícilmente desde la tierra. Estos “círculos” se han encontrado gracias a nuevas imágenes de satélite, con imágenes no similares vistas en otra ubicación de los Estados Unidos de América.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Arqueología, Apache, geo-glifos,

“Dedicated to the Indigenous people who have not survived the Native American Holocaust”

Dear Editor

Marathon is a place located in Brewster County, Texas state, USA (30°12'27"N, 103°14'36"W (Fig. 1), at 1236 m up level, with 13.73 km² of area, 50% of humidity and 26°C of median temperature (USCB 2011).

We have found in the town of Marathon in the north-west Texas, singular circles that can be seen from the space but difficultly from land (Fig. 2). We located these “circles”, thanks to new satellite images, with rather non similar images positioned in other United States of America location.

Letting fly the fantasy, it could possibly be geoglyphs, located in North West's Texas, perhaps would represent a North American similar petite version of the Nazca figures in Perú (South America).

“Circles”, in general, have been suggested as “wheels” by archaeologists, when these rock structures have a drawing, with a group of circles lineated in radial figure. We believe, if they are real and not science fiction, these geoglyphs could be

created by indigenous communities prevalent in the area, most likely the descended from a prehistoric tribe or Paleo-Indians that lived before the Apaches and the Lipan-Apache tribes (Opler 1945, Hester 1991).

The European invaders and explorers wrote the first records we have of the native populations in 1519 AD, long after the Paleo-Indian culture had disappeared. Apaches were among the more important subgroups living around the actual Marathon in Texas, probably date back to antiquity, being the major tribes that existed at the time of the first European exploration. In Marathon, we have observed a stone-built circle, more extensive in the area that no one already saw in the country, such as a small Ceremonial Stone Circle at Gungyswamp, near Groton, Connecticut (Brad 2020). These wheels probably form part of a variety of geoglyphs with magic intentions (Malouf 1961), such as the rain circles describe in many regions of the United States, which are used to induce rain through unknown forces. These comprise inexplicable structures that are sited across the landscape for up to several metres or kilometres and have no perceptible practical use.

Figure 1. Location of Marathon, Texas, USA.

Our observation was looking at archaeological sites across North West Texas using the Google Earth program®. The main questions have been why the circles may be used for, or what meaning they held? We were fascinated by this assembly and studying the structures, as the wheels are difficult to pick up from the land. When we were to the place, we could imagine a little of a pattern but not without difficulty. The circles must have been patent when they were firstly built. But, nowadays many inhabitants have perhaps moved and walked

over the circles for centuries without notice their presence.

The wheels appear to have been no described so far. They were found in isolation near the Marathon town, and in fact quite remarkable, aligned in the similar direction that the sun rises and seeing to the Big Bend mountains to the south ($30^{\circ}12'19.20''$ N - $103^{\circ}15'46.33''$ W) at 1233 m of altitude (Google Earth 2020) (Fig. 3).

Figure 2. The circles of Marathon, Texas, USA.

Figure 3. (A) The grasslands of Marathon, Texas. In the background the mountains of Big Bend. (B) The Big Bend mountains.

Dating the circles is complex, given that they seem to be prehistoric, and if they would be related to the ancient Indians before the Apache people (including the Navajo) whom came from the far North to settle the Plains and from the Southwest around A.D. 850. These circles can be named to as geoglyphs in the same way as the Nazca Lines are referred. The meaning of the circles may also have been analogous to the mysterious drawings in the Peruvian Nazca desert, generally considering, the circles as spaces for rituals associated with seasons or with astronomical phenomena, this structure could have similar function as the Nazca Lines. The design is unlike, but the purpose could be the equivalent. The big problem is what was their purpose?

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